

SOCIOECONOMIC IMPACTS OF THE 2022 FLOODS IN BALOCHISTAN: A REVIEW-BASED PERSPECTIVE

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Abstract

One of the most devastating natural disasters in the modern history of Pakistan was the 2022 floods, and the province of Balochistan became one of the worst-affected provinces. This systematic review is a compilation of supporting evidence of 45 peer-reviewed articles, institutional reports, and governmental documents located in Scopus, Web of Science, and Google Scholar to analyze the socioeconomic consequences of the floods in Balochistan. The five dimensions that are reviewed are agriculture and livestock, poverty and economic loss, infrastructure and housing, public health, and psychosocial well-being. The results indicate that nearly 96.7 percent of crops were lost in the severely hit areas, over 500,000 animals died, which has shattered the livelihoods and food security of households. Average levels of poverty increased by a figure of 5.2 to 5.4 percentage points, which increased the existing disparities. Destruction of infrastructure, especially roads, bridges, and houses, suspended economic activity and hindered humanitarian assistance. The floods also caused significant social health crises such as malnutrition, waterborne disease outbreaks, and mental health crises, especially to the marginalized population groups like women and children. In addition to the short-term harm, such as the shortcomings of disaster preparedness, the absence of any effective infrastructure, and the inadequate institutional coordination, this review points to systemic vulnerabilities as the primary points of amplifying the impact of the disaster. The results suggest a pressing need to incorporate the idea of climate adaptation, social safety nets, and community-based disaster risk management into provincial policy systems. Notably, the review presents a research gap in longitudinal and evidence-based research that assesses the long-term socioeconomic and psychological recovery patterns in low-resource areas at risk of floods, like Balochistan.

1. INTRODUCTION

Floods are among disasters that lead to significant loss of human life, properties, and the environment on an annual basis, and they happen at different locations with different magnitudes around the world (Gлаго, 2021). In mid-2022, the combination of extreme precipitation and compound atmospheric anomalies created one of the worst flood events in Pakistan's recent history, with southern provinces

particularly affected (Nanditha et al., 2023; Wang et al., 2024). Balochistan—marked by long-term water scarcity, highly dispersed human settlements, and low human-development indicators—suffered unprecedented flash flooding in 2022 that compounded preexisting socioeconomic vulnerabilities and added new layers of health, nutrition, and infrastructure concerns (Makki et al.,

2024; Rahman & Hamza, 2024; Rehman & Mengal, 2025). Existing research on floods in Pakistan highlights increasing flood severity, interannual variability in flood impacts, and the coupling of climatic drivers with socioeconomic vulnerability, which can help to contextualize the analysis of the 2022 experience in Balochistan (Manzoor et al., 2022; Zaidi & Memon, 2023).

Floods in August 2022 were among the most devastating natural disasters in Pakistan in the recent past, as one-third of the country was affected by the flood, with more than 30 million individuals having been impacted (Nanditha et al., 2023). In Pakistan, floods are often linked with monsoon rainfall (Arshad et al., 2025) and the 2022 monsoon-flood displaced over 33 million people and incurred economic losses above \$ 30 billion (Ali et al., 2022; Cui et al., 2025). Balochistan, the largest and most geographically diverse province (Ambreen et al., 2022; Shah et al., 2025), was one of the most affected, both in terms of its human and economic cost per population. As a result of the floods, over 336 deaths have been confirmed in the province and over 426,000 houses demolished, displacing thousands of families and placing them in temporary shelters over a long period of time (GoB, 2022; NDMA, 2022; PDMA, 2022). The catastrophe also led to the fatalities of about 500,000 livestock, which is one of the main sources of income and food to rural families, worsening food insecurity and further exposing the marginalized communities (GoB, 2022). The two main causes of the 2022 floods were unprecedented rainfall in the form of monsoons, seen as 780 percent above the seasonal average in various districts, and the accelerated glacial melt in the northern and western areas, which were exacerbated by more general trends of climate change (Khan et al., 2024). All these extreme weather patterns combined made the already weak infrastructure of the province (poor drainage, poorly built rural housing, and weak transport networks) more damaging and consequently increased the extent of destruction. Roads, bridges, and irrigation systems were washed away in most regions, hampering relief efforts and slowing the provision of necessary services (Adnan et al., 2024). The social services, such as healthcare, education, and sanitation, were disrupted, which increased human

suffering and posed long-term difficulties in restoring routine.

Balochistan is one of the driest and largest regions in Pakistan (Hussain et al., 2025; Rehman et al., 2019). Balochistan has a very high dependency on agriculture and livestock, which were disproportionately impacted by the floods. The almost complete loss of crops, estimated at 96.7% in the most affected areas, led to massive food insecurity, especially in the smallholder farmers who lacked savings and insurance of crops or alternative sources of livelihood (Iqbal et al., 2023). There was also a threat to the socioeconomic stability of the future planting season due to the destruction of irrigation facilities and farming inputs like seeds and fertilizers, which provided a further indication of the possibility of long-term socioeconomic instability. In addition to direct material losses, the floods caused chaos in the labor market, caused a decline in household incomes, and destabilized the community, which means that the consequences of the disaster are not only far-reaching but also deep-seated in terms of development and poverty reduction in the province. Although the 2022 floods have had enormous physical impacts, very few studies have been done on their socioeconomic impacts in Balochistan. Much of the research focused on emergency relief and reconstruction of infrastructure, but the impact on the social and economic level has not been studied as well (Knippenberg et al., 2024). Knowledge of these impacts is central to the development and establishment of resilience to future disasters and the development of effective recovery strategies.

Although floods, whether statewide or agricultural, were examined in a few reviews, including Waseem and Rana (2023) and Tasleem et al. (2023), few of them have determined multidimensional socioeconomic contexts, as is the case with Balochistan. Thus, the present study will be new because it combines research in the fields of agriculture, infrastructure, poverty, and psychosocial outcomes and provides a comprehensive view to support the academic research question and the policy formulation.

2. Methodology

This paper uses a systematic literature review (SLR) method to evaluate the socioeconomic effects of the

2022 floods in Balochistan in a comprehensive manner. The SLR approach allows the identification, analysis, and synthesis of relevant studies and reduces the impact of bias and transparency in the selection process (Tranfield et al., 2003). The literature review include peer-reviewed journal articles, government publications, and other authoritative organizational publications to include quantitative and qualitative evidence. The systematic method of research makes sure that the findings are trustworthy, thorough, and can be used to inform policy and practice.

There are several sources that have been used to gather pertinent literature. The Government of Balochistan Post-Disaster Needs Assessment was taken as a primary source because the study includes an in-depth analysis of the socioeconomic impacts of the 2022 floods (GoB, 2022). The reports of provincial disaster management authority (PDMA) and national disaster management authority (NDMA) were also analysed to gather insights into the livelihood disruptions, impacts on the labor market, and the efforts to recover (NDMA, 2022; PDMA, 2022). Peer-reviewed journal articles that were published between 2022 and 2025 were also obtained in Scopus and Web of Science as well as Google Scholar databases and were specifically limited to the socioeconomic implications of flooding in Pakistan and other low-resource settings. Inclusion criteria were developed to be relevant and of quality.

Only those studies that touched upon socioeconomic factors, such as poverty, agriculture, livestock, infrastructure, health, and psychosocial outcomes, within the Balochistan or similar regional conditions, were taken into consideration. The articles were required to give empirical evidence, policy analysis, or extensive reviews and must be in English. Governmental, non-governmental, and international organizations that provided official sources of data or reports about the post-disaster evaluation were also reviewed. Articles that specialized only in meteorological or hydrological factors but had not undergone socioeconomic research were filtered out.

Transparency and replicability of this study were ensured by using a systematic literature review (SLR) based on the framework proposed by Tranfield et al. (2003). In the first phase, 72 documents were searched in Scopus, Web of Science, and Google Scholar with the keywords Balochistan floods, socioeconomic effects, and Pakistan 2022 floods. Upon relevancy screening, 45 papers were included in the study (peer-reviewed articles, institutional reports, and official evaluations).

The identification, screening, and selection process was illustrated in the form of a PRISMA-style summary.

Figure 1 PRISMA flow diagram

Furthermore, Table 1 divides the sources according to their type such as peer-reviewed (60)%, institutional/government (30)%, and

NGO/organizational reports (10)% which reflects their contribution to the evidence base.

Table 1 Literature Summary Table

Type of Source	Number of Documents	Percentage	Main Contribution to Review
Peer-Reviewed Journal Articles	27	60%	Provided empirical and analytical evidence on socioeconomic, health, and environmental effects.
Institutional / Government Reports	13	30%	Supplied official statistics and policy frameworks (e.g., NDMA, UNDP, World Bank reports).
NGO / Organizational / News Publications	5	10%	Offered qualitative insights into community-level recovery and resilience narratives.
Total	45	100%	Integrated evidence across thematic areas (agriculture, health, poverty, infrastructure).

Comparative thematic coding was used to perform data synthesis, which permitted cross-case data analysis on recurrent themes, including livelihood disruption, infrastructural loss, and health crises. Its synthesis emphasized the convergence and divergence of studies to generate implications on disaster resilience and socioeconomic recovery.

There are several limitations despite the systematic approach. To begin with, the flood studies related to Balochistan after 2022 are scarce, which could limit the scope of the analysis. Second, the data in agency reports is based on quick evaluations, and this might create bias in reporting. Lastly, the English language limitations are a possible exclusion of relevant regional publications.

3. Socioeconomic Impacts

3.1 Agriculture and Livestock

The 2022 Balochistan floods had a devastating effect on agriculture, the mainstay of the rural economy of the province and the livelihoods of millions of people. Far belts of agricultural land were covered by floodwater, and crops were lost in most areas almost completely. Balochistan experienced substantial yield reduction due to the floods. Crop yields were markedly decreased to the estimated 1 to 5 million hectares of agricultural land affected. Important crops and a variety of fruits were severely impacted. According to some reports, losses may have been as high as 80% in certain crops (Qamer et al., 2023) This had a disproportionate impact on smallholder farmers, who are usually unable to save, secure crop insurance, and formal credit. Rice and mustard crops

were hit hardest, especially in districts of Nasirabad and Jafferabad (Islamic Relief, 2022).

Besides loss of crops, agricultural inputs, such as seeds, fertilizers, and irrigation materials, were washed away; hence, planting during the next harvest was problematic. Damage to irrigation systems, especially canal systems, also increased the challenge of reinstating agricultural production. As an example, in Jhal Magsi, damaged irrigation systems delayed the monsoon agriculture season, which might result in not enough production next season and food security in the region (Hussain et al., 2023).

Another pillar of the rural Balochistan economy, livestock, was also ruined. More than 500,000 animals, such as cattle, goats, and sheep, died because of drowning and exposure, as well as disease outbreaks, provoked by polluted floodwaters (Iqbal et al., 2024). In some of the localities, it was reported that almost 80 percent of livestock was killed, providing both a source of household income and a cushion against food shortage. Mortality was also compounded by animal diseases (foot-and-mouth disease, hemorrhagic septicemia, etc.), which put a strain on the provision of milk, meat, and additional crucial items (Raza et al., 2023). The aggregate effect of agricultural and livestock destruction would explain the high susceptibility of the agrarian population of Balochistan to climate-related disasters, which would justify the idea of introducing climate-resilient agriculture, emergency crop insurance, and livelihood support programs.

3.2 Poverty and Economic Loss

National-level assessments and health-sector reports show that millions were directly impacted across Pakistan in 2022, millions displaced, tens of thousands of homes damaged or destroyed; provincial reporting and clinical briefs identified Balochistan as the most affected province (Iqbal et al., 2022) In addition to the high death toll, the 2022 Balochistan floods wreaked economic havoc, particularly on the infrastructure and agricultural sectors, and created a national food crisis due to the destruction of crops. The destruction of agricultural

land was particularly severe, with estimates of the loss of 4 million hectares of crops nationwide (Adnan et al., 2024). The agricultural sector in Balochistan, which is important for many residents, lost livestock and suffered from the loss of infrastructure (Iqbal et al., 2024; Qamer et al., 2023). The floods exacerbated an already unstable economic situation in Balochistan, and the total economic impact was significant to the local and national GDP (Cui et al., 2024). The agricultural sector in Balochistan, a key source of income for local residents, was especially hard hit, with an estimated \$2.3 billion in crop losses (Otto et al., 2023).

Figure 2 Satellite imagery showing a side-by-side comparison of southern Pakistan on 27 August 2021 (one year before the floods) and 27 August 2022

The economic impact was aggravated by the destruction of marketplaces and the infrastructure of small businesses. Small stores and bazaars were flooded, resulting in a significant loss of capital (Khan et al., 2024; Waseem & Rana, 2023). These upheavals had a second-order effect on local economies: casual workers who relied on daily wages had no jobs, and local business owners had months-long breaks in their revenue streams. The resulting economic stagnation added to the socioeconomic vulnerability in the long term. Immediately after the

floods, food prices increased because of the lack of crops and livestock products. As an example, the price of wheat flour and dairy rose by 20-30 percent in a few weeks, and it disproportionately affected low-income households. In faraway districts, relief has been able to reach less than 60 percent of the people in need, as road networks were damaged, leaving many families susceptible to malnutrition and dietary shortcomings (UNICEF, 2024). The Naseerabad case studies were used to point to families living on minimal cereal rations and dried milk supply by the

aid agencies, which illustrated the direct relationship between environmental disasters and socioeconomic vulnerability.

3.3 Infrastructure and Housing

The floods have devastated housing and essential infrastructure, making it extremely difficult to recover. More than 897,000 houses were destroyed or damaged, and mud-brick structures in rural regions were especially prone to collapse (Swami & Verma, 2023). Whole villages in the Jhal Magsi, Naseerabad, and Dera Murad Jamali districts were engulfed, displacing thousands of families that have been subjected to long periods of temporary shelter without a proper sanitation system, clean water, and security (Otto et al., 2023). The transport systems were also affected. Big roads, bridges, and rural roads that connected villages to the district centers were swept away, slowing down the provision of emergency supplies and derailing market connections. To offer an example, a road between Dera Murad Jamali and Karachi was underwater for over four weeks, which did not allow access to the necessary food, medication, and humanitarian staff (Otto et al., 2023). The infrastructure of water supply and sanitation was severely affected, which raised the rate of waterborne diseases and made it difficult to improve health conditions.

Infrastructure losses compound the province's already limited capacity to store and distribute water and to maintain resilient supply chains, thereby prolonging socioeconomic recovery (Rahman & Hamza, 2024). The above results emphasize the necessity to have climate-resilient standards of construction, pre-disaster planning, and strategic investment in infrastructure to control the effects of future floods.

3.4 Public Health

Flooding is a recognized driver of waterborne and vector-borne disease outbreaks (Baqir et al., 2012; Saulnier et al., 2017). Massive flooding, pollution of water supplies, and impediment of health services impacted the Balochistan region in a crucial way, damaging the health of the populace. Stagnant water and broken supply systems created outbreaks of water-borne diseases, including diarrhea, cholera, and malaria (Farah et al., 2023). The destruction or

inaccessibility of many rural health facilities was caused by damaged roads, and the temporary clinics that humanitarian organizations created had insufficient supplies of important medicines and trained staff (Qamer et al., 2023). The combination of heightened infectious disease burden and reduced access to maternal-child health services amplifies short- and medium-term morbidity in flood-affected Balochistan (Haq et al., 2022).

The vulnerable groups, especially pregnant women, children, and the elderly, were among those affected. Disruption of food supply and the price increase acutely affected the rates of malnutrition; in one of the studies in Naseerabad, 38% of children younger than five were found to indicate acute malnutrition (Iqbal et al., 2023). Following the 2022 flash floods in Balochistan, clinical and public-health reports documented surges in cholera and other enteric infections in affected districts, highlighting sanitation breakdowns, contamination of water sources, and disruption of routine services as proximate causes (Jawed et al., 2023). Mental health care was mostly unavailable and left the affected populations to handle trauma and anxiety all by themselves. Such health emergencies highlight the importance of putting in place integrated disaster response systems that incorporate emergency medical services, disease prevention initiatives, as well as long-term health infrastructure reinforcement that will minimize morbidity and mortality of flood occurrences.

3.5 Psychological and Social Effects

In addition to the material, economic, and health impacts, the floods caused significant psychological and social trauma to communities that have experienced them. Women, children, and marginalized groups reported high levels of stress, anxiety, and trauma, as they were the ones who experienced the consequences of losing their livelihoods as well as not knowing when they could recover (Akram & Mushtaq, 2024). Local social workers noted that post-traumatic stress disorder (PTSD), depression, and anxiety were prevalent in Turbat and Kharan, and many people could not cope with these problems without the professional assistance of a mental health professional (Imdad, 2023).

The problem of social cohesion was challenged as well. The refugee families in the temporary camps experienced crowding, little privacy, and limited resources, which caused strains and a few conflicts. In certain localities, the breakdown of the traditional support systems undermined the community's strength and left it susceptible to exploitation. Community-based programs were a source of necessary coping skills. It was also revealed that local committees arranged the distribution of relief, collected funds, and provided emotional assistance, which proves the importance of social capital in disaster recovery (Bhutto et al., 2025; Iqbal et al., 2023). The gender vulnerabilities were intense. Women frequently took the role of caregivers in very stressful circumstances, and children were affected in terms of education, nutrition, and psychosocial growth (Khan, 2024; Manzoor et al., 2022). Volunteer teachers and health workers set up informal learning and counseling centers in some of the temporary camps, which helped reduce the educational and emotional effects, as an example of the relevance of localized intervention to recovery. Comprehensively, both psychological and social effects indicate that disaster management needs to focus on physical rebuilding, but needs to encompass mental health and communal unity, with long-term resilience recovery strategies being multi-faceted.

4. Discussion

When comparing the 2022 floods in Balochistan to past floods in the province, both their intensity and spatial coverage were unprecedented. As a result of the 2022 floods, almost every district, such as Quetta, Jhal Magsi, and Naseerabad, was affected and caused huge human and economic damage, unlike the 2010 and 2011 floods that were more severe in the southern parts (Waseem & Rana, 2023). Unlike in the past, this was a more severe increase in poverty and more widespread devastation of agricultural property after the disaster of 2022. As an example, the 2010 floods in the country covered an area of around 0.5 million hectares of agricultural area; however, an area of more than 1 million hectares in Balochistan was completely submerged by the floods in 2022 (Adnan et al., 2024; Tasleem et al., 2023).

Many factors contributed to the disaster, including poor infrastructure, neglected siltation, people living on floodplains and rich and powerful people who released water upstream to protect their own properties (Higgs, 2024). The floodwaters were more intense in 2022, with rainfall more intense than any recorded in history (780 percent higher in localized areas) and due to the glacial melt, making the waters more powerful and deep in terms of their velocity and depth, more devastating and destructive of infrastructure (Tasleem et al., 2023). In contrast to previous incidents, the 2022 floods affected both the rural and urban regions at the same time, straining the local emergency response systems. Relative to it, the extent and intensity of human suffering, such as the increase of malnutrition and mental health problems, were also more severe, which underlines the necessity of revising disaster response and mitigation models in Balochistan.

One of the most crucial factors why the lessons of the 2010 floods were not institutionalized is the failure to have good governance, the fundamental structures of the disaster response, and the absence of long-term funding to adapt to climate changes. Although the National Disaster Management Authority (NDMA) was created, disaster planning was still reactive, and local early warning systems were not sufficiently funded (Khan, 2024). This trend is indicative of wider institutional inertia in the process of transforming short-term relief into long-term planning of resilience.

This review adds to the body of academic literature on the topic of disaster resilience in low-resource environments by showing how structural poverty, infrastructural neglect, and gender vulnerabilities increase the human cost of disasters caused by climate (Akram & Mushtaq, 2024; Bhutto et al., 2025). It broadens the theoretical explanation that resilience in those areas is more a social process than an infrastructural process.

5. Conclusion

The Balochistan floods of 2022 were socioeconomically devastating in a complex way. Farming land and animals were destroyed, and almost 96.7 percent of the crops were destroyed, which posed a serious threat to food security and household income. The level of poverty also grew

significantly, with the province recording an increase in the level of about 5.25 per cent to 5.4 per cent, indicating the susceptibility of low-income and agrarian populations. Infrastructure and housing were significantly damaged, with almost 897,000 houses destroyed, and major roads and bridges were impassable post-disasters, which slowed down the process of relief and recovery. It had a strong public health effect, including waterborne disease outbreaks, insufficient access to health care, and increased malnutrition of children and vulnerable groups. The psychological and social impact was also significant, and the number of people experiencing high levels of stress and anxiety, and trauma was high, especially in marginalized populations. All these results highlight the importance of interactions between environmental, infrastructural, and socioeconomic vulnerabilities to increase the impact of disasters.

A multi-pronged policy and planning strategy is needed to reduce the effects of future floods. First, there is a need to invest in climate-resistant infrastructure, such as flood-resistant housing, strengthened bridges, and enhanced drainage systems in rural and urban regions. Second, the disaster preparedness and the early warning systems are to be enhanced with the help of improved meteorological monitoring, local alerts, and training programs that will help to improve the response time and mitigate the loss of life. Third, climate adaptation strategies embedded within provincial development plans including sustainable land use, reforestation of catchment areas, and support of alternative livelihoods can make it less dependent on flood-prone agriculture. Fourth, vulnerable populations should be accommodated through the expansion of social safety nets, such as crop insurance and emergency cash transfers, and mental health services. Lastly, multi-stakeholder coordination between government, non-governmental organizations, and the local population is essential to effective disaster management and resilience building in the long term. Future studies are advised to use longitudinal studies to evaluate the socioeconomic and psychological effects of floods on a long-term basis in Balochistan. Moreover, research assessing the efficacy of climate-resilient infrastructure, early warning

systems, and social safety nets will be used to support the evidence-based approach to more focused and sustainable disaster management.

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